

MATHEMATICAL CO-RELATION IN TYPES OF ORGANIC REACTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Substitution, addition and elimination organic reactions have been represented in mathematical numerical form. In mathematical numerical form, the total number of species in reactant (S) left side and product (S) right side are equal in substitution reactions while reactant (S) left side are always more than product (S) right side in addition reactions and product (S) on right side are more than reactant (S) in left side in elimination reactions. Mathematical Co- relation has been made in which addition cum elimination or elimination cum addition is substitution, which has been explained with suitable examples.

Keywords: substitution, addition, elimination, rearrangement and correlation.

Introduction:

Most organic reactions involve conversion of one functional group into another by the attack of reagent i.e. by electrophile (electron deficient species)/ Nucleophile (electron efficient species)/ free radical (odd electron species) and the organic reaction may be represented as:

Any classification of organic reaction must emphasize the changes to occur in the substrate at the site of the reaction by heterolytic or homolytic cleavage so the structure of substrate changes fundamentally. In this way organic reactions may be placed in four major groups i.e. four types of organic reactions¹⁻⁶

1. Substitution reaction
2. Addition reaction
3. Elimination reaction
4. Rearrangement reaction

Results and Discussion:

1. Substitution Reaction-

Reaction in which atom or group directly linked to a carbon atom is replaced by another atom or group, are called substitution reactions.^{1,5} In such reaction the bonds are broken and formed at the same carbon, which is considered, to be the reactive site of the substrate i.e. hybridization state remains unchanged. Again the substitution may be initiated by an electrophile, nucleophile or free radical resulting in three categories of each type. Some examples are given below:

In all the above cases, if we consider total number of species of reactant (S) and product (S) side in mathematical numerical form, then substitution reaction can be represented as:

The total number of species are two in reactant (S) left side and also two species in product (S) right side.

So another way of explanation of substitution reaction in mathematical form can be explained as-

“ In mathematical numerical forms substitution reactions are those in which total number of species in reactant (S) left side and product (S) right side are equal”

2.Addition Reaction-

Those reactions in which the attacking reagent adds to the substrate molecule.³⁻⁴ In this process triple bond may be converted to a double bond or single bond and a double bond converts into single bond. π bond of the molecule is converting into σ bond, so the hybridization state is changing from $SP - SP^2$ and $SP^2 - SP^3$. Like substitution, addition reactions can also have classified into categories of initiating reagents. Few examples of addition reactions are given below:

In all the above reactions, if we consider the total number of species of reactant (S) and product (S) in mathematical numerical form, then the addition reaction can be represented as:

The total number of species are two in reactant (S) left side while the total number of species is one in the product (S) right side.

So another way of addition reactions in mathematical form can be as follows:

“ In mathematical numerical form, addition reaction are those in which total number of species in reactant (S) left side is always more by one than in product (S) right side”

3.Elimination Reaction:

The reverse of addition reaction is elimination reaction. In elimination reactions the number of groups or atoms attached to carbon decrease and the degree of the unsaturation in the molecule increases.⁴⁻⁶ In essence σ bonds are converted to π bonds. State of hybridization of carbon changes from $\text{SP}^3 - \text{SP}^2$ and $\text{SP}^2 - \text{SP}$. Elimination are generally classified on the basis of molecularity of the reaction. Few examples are given below:

In the above cases, if we consider total number species of reactant (S) on left side and product (S) on right side, in mathematical numerical form, then elimination reaction can be represented as:

The total number of specie is one in reactant (S) left side while the total number of species are two in the product (S) right side.

So the mathematical form of elimination reaction can be as follow:

“ In mathematical numerical form, elimination reactions are those in which total number of specie in reactant (S) left side is always less by one than in product (S) right side”

Elimination **(E)**

$$(m = m^\otimes + m^\otimes\otimes)$$

4. Rearrangement-

These reactions occur with more stability of intermediate species i.e. rearranges by a group or atom for more stable form. Here hyperconjugation plays an important role in rearrangement. Example of rearrangement reactions are as follows –

Mathematical Co-Relation:

5. Co-Relation-

So over all, we can write substitution addition and elimination reaction in mathematical numerical form as:

If we co- relate these, then

(i) a = b cum c i.e. S = A cum E

(ii) a = c cum b i.e. S = E cum A

(Mathematical Corelation)

Explanation with few suitable examples:

(i) Substitution reactions are addition cum elimination reactions. [1,5-6] Firstly, addition reaction occurs which is followed by elimination and overall it become substitution.

S_N2 Mechanism, Backside Attack with Inversion

OR

Methyl alcohol

(ii) Substitution reactions are elimination cum addition reactions, [1,5-6] Firstly, elimination reaction occurs which is followed by addition and overall it becomes substitution.

Few examples of this type are as follows:

S_N1 Mechanism

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Conflict of Interest

Author confirmed that there is no conflict of interest.

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